

Exploring English Idioms in the Song Lyrics of the “Cannot Be, Whatsoever” Album by Novo Amor

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to find the types of idioms in the song lyrics of the “Cannot Be, Whatsoever” album by Novo Amor. This research used descriptive research with synchronic linguistics analysis. The researcher analyzed 9 (nine) songs. They are *Opaline*, *I Feel Better*, *Decimal*, *No Plans*, *Birdcage*, *Keep Me*, *Halloween*, *If We’re Being Honest*, and *Guest Book*. The researcher analyzed the idiomatic expression types using the theory of Makkai, which classifies the idioms based on the structures. Besides that, the researcher used idiom similarity in the idiom dictionary to find the meaning of the idioms. From the analysis, the researcher found 63 idiomatic expressions in the song lyrics of the songs in the “Cannot Be, Whatsoever” album by Novo Amor. The idiom types according to Makkai’s theory that was found in this album were 10 Phrasal Verb Idioms, 44 Tournure Idioms, 1 Irreversible Binomial Idioms, and 8 Phrasal Compound Idioms. It can be said that the dominant type of Makkai’s theory in this album’s songs is the Tournure Idiom, and the least type is the Irreversible Binomial Idiom.

1. Introduction

Bram & Avillanova (2019, p. 247) stated that English songs are increasingly used by teachers in the classroom to help students improve their English abilities. Songs are usually written beautifully with such nice words that they attract people and hold listeners’ attention. When it comes to something interesting, it can be easily memorized by students. Especially with the increasing use of songs on social media that can attract students’ attention. Therefore, as songs are one of the interesting ways to learn English, they are used as learning media in Indonesian schools. Wahyuningrum (2019) in her research entitled “*Pengaruh Penggunaan Media Lagu Terhadap Penguasaan Kosakata Bahasa Inggris di STIPAS Tahasak Danum Pabelum Palangka Raya*”, has conducted experimental research using pre-test and post-test research design to find out the effect of using song media on English vocabulary mastery. The results showed that there was an effect of using song media on better English

vocabulary mastery. Therefore, of the many ways to learn English, the song is one of the most effective media.

When we analyze and learn a song, we may indirectly acquire four language skills that are speaking, listening, writing, and reading (Wahyudi, 2016, p. 120). If we pay attention to some songs, it can be seen that most of the lyrics in songs have content like poems or poetry. Song lyrics are also valuable since they are a form of poetry, and it is not for nothing that popular music appeals to such a large and diverse audience (West, 2019, p. 4). So, it usually contains a figure of speech. One of them is part of the figure of speech that is called an idiom.

An idiom is a collection of words that, when put together, have a meaning that is different from the meaning of the individual words that make it up (Putu et al, 2016, p. 261). Therefore, words that used as idioms are generally will be difficult to understand if they are not adapted to the context being discussed. In song lyrics, the songwriter can use the idiom as freely as he wants to convey the message in the song. Sometimes it is an idiom that is already used in everyday language usage, such as "a piece of cake", which means something is very easy, "to pick up the phone", which means to answer the phone, and "hold on", which means wait; stop. Idioms also appear in songs that are used or made to relate to the song lyrics. When we find new idiomatic expressions, we have to interpret them by ourselves. So, that is what makes idioms interesting to learn, as idioms cannot be interpreted word-for-word. Sometimes it is easy if we find common idioms that we often use, but it will be difficult if we find rarely used idioms.

At the university level, idioms are studied in English literature courses and English language courses, for example in lexical studies subjects. In learning about the topic of songs, students are expected to be able to find meaning in songs. Related to the previous explanations, idioms can appear at any time in a song. Idioms can also appear in any other English topic implicitly since common idioms such as "hold on", "pick up", "after all", "give up", etc. usually appear in everyday English usage.

To solve the difficulty of learning idioms, it must be remembered that sometimes the words in the idiom itself are not the real meaning, they have different meanings. Based on the condition that was explained above, the researcher conducted a study about the analysis of idioms that are found in the song lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor. The researcher chose this album because there are a lot of idioms in these songs. He is famous as a folklore genre singer who conveys the message of his song with beautiful lyrics. Before this album was released, many of his fans were looking forward to this album. This can be seen from the responses of Novo Amor's fans on the comments page of the original Youtube channel of Novo Amor, named "Novo Amor". Therefore, the researcher conducted this research on the subject of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor. This research is expected to contribute academically and bring innovation to the educational field as teaching materials about idioms.

There are some researchers have analyzed idiomatic expressions in song lyrics. First is research that was carried out by Wahyudi (2016). In this study, he identified the types of idioms in the song lyrics of the albums "Roll On" and "State of Emergency" by The Living End, then Wahyudi described the meaning of the idioms from the song. This study used theory from Ogden and Richards (1976) about semantic triangles and from F.R. Palmer

(1976) about types of idioms to analyze the idiomatic expressions found in the songs. This research used a descriptive qualitative method. The findings of this study indicate that there are three types of idioms, such as phrasal verbs, prepositional verb sequences, and one-sided idioms. In addition, the meanings of idioms can be seen in the contexts in which they occur to understand the meaning of idioms more fully. Another study was carried out by Rosyada (2019). She analyzed and interpreted the types of idioms in Green Day's song lyrics from the seventh album of American Idiot. This study used theories from Makkai (1994) and Lyons (1984) to find out the types of idiomatic expressions in song lyrics and to convey the meaning. The findings of this study indicate that in Green Day's song lyrics from the seventh album of American Idiot there are all types of idioms, they are Phrasal Compound Idioms, Phrasal Verb Idioms, Irreversible Binomial Idioms, Tournure Idioms, Incorporating Verb Idioms. This study's findings for meaning delivery show that half of the data has the same lexical and contextual meanings, and the other half has different meanings between lexical and contextual meanings. Therefore, the gap between the previous researches and this research was on the subject of the study and the use of idiom dictionaries as support to collect and analyze the data. The research analyzing the meaning of idioms by using the idiom dictionaries such as *Dictionary of American Idioms*, *the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms*, *The Free Online Dictionary*, *the Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary*, and *the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Online Dictionary*. The subject of this research is the songs from the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor.

The researcher conducted this study under the title "Exploring English Idioms in the Song Lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" Album by Novo Amor" to find idiomatic expressions to categorize them into their types. The researcher conducted this research as descriptive research with synchronic linguistics analysis. The researcher categorized the idiomatic expressions using the theory of Makkai (1994), which classifies the idioms based on the structures. The researcher chose Makkai's theory because this theory has been used by many previous researchers who researched the types of idioms. Besides that, the researcher used Makkai's theory was also because Makkai included phrasal verbs as one of the types of idioms, even though many people still debate whether the phrasal verb itself is idiomatic or not. On the other hand, the researcher interpreted the idioms using some idiom dictionaries.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Definition of Idiom

There are phrases in every language that cannot be translated word for word such as idiom. The researcher used the theory of Makkai (1994) to define an idiom. According to Makkai (1994), an idiom is a form which (a) contains more than one minimal free form (i.e., word), (b) has a literal meaning, which is obtained in the usual way by taking account of the meanings of its constituents and their structural relations, and (c) also has a different meaning which can only be assigned to the whole form. From the definition above, it means that idioms cannot be found with their meaning word for word, but in the context of the sentence.

2.2 Types of Idioms

In this research, the researcher used the theory of idiom types by Makkai (1994) in his book, "Idiomatic Structure in English". Makkai divides idioms with the name of lexemic idiom into five types:

a. Phrasal Verb Idiom

An idiom can be classified as a Phrasal Verb Idiom if it includes a verb and a particle (adverb and/or preposition). Most Phrasal Verb Idioms are made up of a limited number of verbs (come, get, go, sit, and so on) and a small number of particles (in, out, away, off, and so on). "Get up", "Come out", "Come out with", "Get away with", and "Get down" are examples of this type.

b. Tournure Idiom

Tournure Idiom is the largest lexemic idiom, it has a bigger size level than the other idioms that have only two words and word-level idioms. This idiom has at least three words. Therefore, Tournure Idiom is the most commonly included in sentences. The format of Tournure Idiom can contain the compulsory "it" (e.g. "to step on it"), definite and indefinite articles (e.g. "to hit the books"), an irreversible binomial (e.g. "to rain cats and dogs"), a phrasal verb (e.g. "to dance on air"), and "be" as a lead (e.g. "to be well off").

c. Irreversible Binominal Idiom

The Irreversible Binomial Idiom is an idiom that is made up of two words joined by a conjunction. In this form, the word order is stable and permanent (e.g. "cats and dogs", "class against class", and "sink or swim").

d. Phrasal Compound Idiom

Phrasal Compound Idiom is commonly an idiom whose words are united into one and form a single thought. This type of idiom has various word combinations such as adjective + noun, noun + noun, verb + noun, and so on. Any kind of words that are combined into one, then it tuned be phrasal, it's automatically an idiom. It can function as a verb, adjective, or noun (e.g. "fish fry", "black market", and "egghead").

e. Incorporating Verb Idiom

Incorporating Verb Idiom is an idiomatic expression that is usually used in formal terms. This type of idiom is present in all of our daily actions, even if we do not realize it. Usually, Incorporating Verb Idiom is separated by (-), but some of them are not. Incorporating Verb Idiom is a kind of idiom that contains the first element (either a noun or an adjective) fastened upon a verb. This idiom is usually used as a verb as well (e.g "sight-see", "wife-hunt", and "eavesdrop").

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research was descriptive research with a synchronic linguistics analysis. Synchronic linguistics, also known as descriptive linguistics, is a linguistics study that studies languages that live in a certain unit of time that is considered relatively short (Azwardi, 2018, p. 93). Another statement was stated by Mahsun (2012) that synchronic language research is language research conducted by observing the phenomenon of a language at a certain time so that it is descriptive. These statements are in line with this research, which was described, analyzed, and interpreted data in the form of idioms in the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album, the latest album from Novo Amor.

3.2 Research Subject

In this study, the researcher must decide on the subject of the study or the sample research to obtain information. The subject of this research was the song lyrics in the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor, which were suspected to contain idiomatic expressions. The researcher chose Novo Amor because he is well-known as a folk musician, which is a musician with an old-school music style that prioritizes lyrics and meaning conveying. With that reputation, the researcher wanted to explore Novo Amor's songs. The "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album is the latest album by Novo Amor from the other 4 albums. This album was released at the end of 2020. Based on the chart from the Best Ever Albums website, the album "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" is Novo Amor's best album among his other albums. This album has 9 songs. According to Arikunto (2013) cited in Azwardi (2018), if the number of research subjects is less than 100, then all of them are taken for data collection. Therefore, all 9 of these songs were taken as samples for this research.

3.3 Research Instrument

In this research, the instrument is the researcher herself. The researcher has a role as the human instrument who knows the theoretical foundation of the problem (Ary et al, 2010). The researcher who functions as a human instrument must carry out activities from determining the research focus to building conclusions from the research. For this reason, "the researcher is the key instrument" in this research. Hence, the researcher must understand the methodology and theory used in the research.

3.4 Data and Data Source

The researcher required sources to collect data. The data source is the subject of the study, which was the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor, and it was from this source that the researcher would obtain the information required. As a result, when performing research, the data sources are crucial. In this research, the data were the primary data in the form of song lyrics in the album "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" by Novo Amor, and also secondary data, that are supporting documents such as the biography of Novo Amor and the official internet site, novoamor.co.uk, from which the song lyrics were taken.

3.5 Data Collection Technique

In this research, the researcher used a data collection technique that has been adapted based on synchronic linguistics or synchronic language research. The method that was used was the *simak* method. The *simak* method is a way of collecting data through listening,

writing, or noting the use of language, both spoken and written (Azwardi, 2018, p. 103). In this case, it was a written language. This method has both basic and advanced techniques. The basic technique that was used was the *sadap* technique. As cited by Azwardi (2018), the basic technique is the *sadap* technique, which is to obtain data by noting the language. Meanwhile, the advanced techniques that were applied were the *Simak Bebas Libat Cakap* (SBLC) technique and the *catat* technique. In the SBLC technique, the researcher only acts as an observer of the use of language without being involved or changing the subject. In conjunction with the SBLC technique, the researcher could use the *catat* technique. The *catat* technique is used if the researcher is dealing with the use of written language. The researcher can write several forms that are relevant to the research from the use of written language (Mahsun, 2012, p. 93). Therefore, the data were taken by observing the official website of Novo Amor, *novoamor.co.uk.*, then taking the song lyrics transcriptions from the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album.

3.6 Data Analysis Method

In this research, the researcher used synchronic linguistics analysis, also known as descriptive linguistics, to analyze the data with the implementation of the *padan intralingual* method and *Hubung Banding Menyamakan* technique (HBS). The *padan intralingual* method is an analytical method by connects elements that are lingual in nature (elements that are in the language) (Azwardi, 2018, p. 109). Meanwhile, HBS is a data analysis technique that equates linguistic units with their comparison tools to determine their identity (Azwardi, 2018, p. 110). The steps in this data analysis method were as follows:

- a. Reading and identifying the whole lyrics that have been retrieved to find the idiomatic expressions supported by idiom dictionaries. The choices of dictionaries used by the researcher are "Dictionary of American Idioms, the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms, The Free Online Dictionary, the Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary, and the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Online Dictionary".
- b. The researcher classified the collected data into their types by implementing the theoretical triangulation, which uses the theory of Makkai (1994) about idiom classification based on their structure.
- c. The researcher explained the meaning of idiomatic expressions using idiom dictionaries by finding similar idioms.
- d. The researcher implemented the investigator triangulation method by discussing with supervisors the findings.
- e. The researcher rechecked from the beginning to the end of the process to draw a conclusion based on the data analysis.

4. Findings

This study analyzed the types of idiomatic expressions found in the 9 song lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor using the theory of Makkai (1994) about idiom classification based on their structure, which is divided into five categories: Phrasal Verb Idiom, Tournure Idiom, Irreversible Binomial Idiom, Phrasal Compound Idiom, and Incorporating Verb Idiom. According to Makkai, essential idiomatic characteristics are those expressions that must be misleading or not caught by an inattentive listener or reader. The idiom types according to Makkai's theory that was found in this album were 63 idiomatic expressions in four types of the idiom. The analysis of the data are as follows:

1. Phrasal Verb Idiom

According to Makkai (1994), an idiom can be classified as a Phrasal Verb Idiom if it includes a verb and a particle (adverb and/or preposition). In this research, the researcher found 10 Phrasal Verb Idioms. The examples are as follows:

a. Example 1

Idiomatic expression : Give up
Title of song : I Feel Better
Lyrics : "I **give up** all of my life"
Context : He no longer hopes for anything in his life.

In the 2nd line of the I Feel Better song lyrics, "I give up all of my life", there is an idiom "**give up**". This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Verb Idiom type, that is formed from Verb + Adverb. The idiom "**give up**" does not use the literal meaning of "**give**" and "**up**", but is interpreted in other ways. The meaning of the idiom "**give up**", based on the Dictionary of American Idioms, is 1) to give up trying to keep; surrender; yield. 2) to stop doing or having something; to abandon; to quit. 3) to stop hoping, waiting, or attempting to do something. 4) to stop trying; quit. In conclusion, "**give up**" means stop trying or stop hoping. Therefore, it is not related to giving something.

b. Example 2

Idiomatic expression : Open up
Title of song : I Feel Better
Lyrics : "but won't you let me **open up** sometime?"
Context : He asked if he could talk about his feelings freely.

In the 9th line of the I Feel Better song lyrics, "but won't you let me open up sometime?", there is an idiom "**open up**". This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Verb Idiom type, which is formed from Verb + Adverb. The meaning of the idiom "**open up**" has nothing to do with the literal meaning of "**open**" and "**up**". The meaning of the idiom "**open up**", based on the Dictionary of American Idioms, means to make clear; to talk frankly or talk freely about your feelings. Therefore, it does not take the meaning of "**open**" which is to cause something to move so that it is no longer closed, or the meaning to start something.

c. Example 3

Idiomatic expression : Carried away
Title of song : Halloween
Lyrics : "I get **carried away** with being **carried away**"
Context : He felt a strong emotion that further strengthened all the existing emotions.

In the 8th line of the Halloween song lyrics, "I get carried away with being carried away", there is an idiom "**carried away**". This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Verb Idiom type, which is formed from Verb + Adverb. The meaning of the idiom "**carried away**" has nothing to do with the literal meaning of "**carried**" and "**away**". The literal meaning of "**carried**", as in "**carry**", is to hold something or someone with your part of the body, whereas the literal meaning of "**away**", is somewhere else, or in a different place, position, or situation; at a distance; mostly or completely gone. According to the Dictionary of American Idioms, the meaning of the idiom "**carried away**", is to cause

very strong feelings; excite or delight to the loss of cool judgment; become so excited that you lose self-control.

2. Tournure Idiom

According to Makkai (1994), a Tournure Idiom type is the largest lexemic idiom type, it has a bigger size level than the other idioms that have only two words and word-level idioms. This idiom has at least three words. In this research, the researcher found 44 Tournure Idioms. The examples are as follows:

a. Example 1

Idiomatic expression : Sit it out

Title of song : No Plans

Lyrics : **"sit it out, sweat it out"**

Context : He forced himself to wait anxiously for something.

In the 5th and 12th lines of the No Plans song lyrics, "sit it out, sweat it out", there is an idiom **"sit it out"**. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type, which contains three words with the compulsory **"it"**. The meaning of the idiom **"sit it out"** has no relation to making something sit. The meaning of the idiom **"sit it out"**, based on the Dictionary of American Idioms, is to wait until an unpleasant or taxing situation passes.

b. Example 2

Idiomatic expression : The rain came down in the shape of everything

Title of song : Keep Me

Lyrics : **"all of the rain came down in the shape of everything"**

Context : He spoke about everything had fallen by force.

In the 9th line of the Keep Me song lyrics, "all of the rain came down in the shape of everything", there is an idiom **"the rain came down in the shape of everything"**. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type, which contains nine words with the compulsory definite article **"the"**. The idiom **"the rain came down in the shape of everything"** has nothing to do with the literal meaning of **"rain"**, which means water that falls in drops from the clouds. The meaning of the idiom **"the rain came down in the shape of everything"** can be adapted from the idiom **"rain (something) down"**, taken from the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Online Dictionary, which means to fall in large amounts, or to direct something in large amounts, usually forcefully or violently. In this case, the meaning can be interpreted as everything (emotion, situation, or something) falling forcefully.

c. Example 3

Idiomatic expression : The ceiling is all coming down

Title of song : Opaline

Lyrics : **"the ceiling is all coming down"**

Context : Everything goes wrong or nothing works out.

The 10th line of the Opaline song lyrics, "the ceiling is all coming down", is an idiomatic expression. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type, which contains six words with the compulsory definite article **"the"**. The meaning of the idiom **"the ceiling is all coming down"** has nothing to do with a ceiling that is coming down. The literal meaning of **"ceiling"** is an overhead interior surface that covers the upper limits of a room. The meaning of the idiom **"the ceiling is all coming down"** can be equated

with the idiom **"the roof falls in"**, taken from the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms, which means everything goes wrong. This equation is taken from the words **"roof"** as the equivalent of the word **"ceiling"**, and the word "falls" as the equivalent of the word **"coming down"**.

d. Example 4

Idiomatic expression : Bend my arm
Title of song : Decimal
Lyrics : **"bend my arm**, I won't be so far at all"
Context : He asks his lover to depend on him to do everything, as he will not go far.

In the 15th line of the Decimal song lyrics, "bend my arm, I won't be so far at all", there is an idiom **"bend my arm"**. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type, which contains three words. The idiom **"bend my arm"** has nothing to do with the literal meaning of **"bend"**, which means to move your body or part of your body so that it is not straight, and has also nothing to do with the literal meaning of **"arm"**, which is part of the upper body. The meaning of the idiom **"bend my arm"** can be adapted from the idiom **"twist one's arm"**, taken from the Dictionary of American Idioms, which means to force someone; or threaten someone to do something. This idiom equation is taken because **"twist"** is a synonym for **"bend"**. Besides that, there is also the same word **"arm"**.

e. Example 5

Idiomatic expression : I wasn't gold
Title of song : No Plans
Lyrics : "cause **I wasn't gold**, I know"
Context : He knows that he was not a person who behaved well.

In the 3rd line of the No Plans song lyrics, "cause I wasn't gold, I know", there is an idiom **"I wasn't gold"**. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type because it contains three words. The idiom **"I wasn't gold"** stressed the word **"gold"**, which has a literal meaning of yellow precious metal; a color of deep yellow. However, the expression **"I wasn't gold"** has nothing to do with gold. Based on the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms, there is an idiom **"as good as gold"**, which means extremely well-behaved. It can be adapted with the idiom **"I wasn't gold"** to interpret the meaning because both idioms emphasize the word **"gold"**. Therefore, the meaning of the idiom **"I wasn't gold"** is that I didn't have good manners before.

f. Example 6

Idiomatic expression : Made my mind up
Title of song : No Plans
Lyrics : **"I made my mind up"**
Context : He had already decided on what was on his mind.

In the 17th line of the No Plans song lyrics, "I made my mind up", there is an idiom **"made my mind up"**. This idiom is categorized as a Tournure Idiom type, which contains four words. The idiom **"made my mind up"** has nothing to do with the literal meaning of **"mind"** and **"up"**. The literal meaning of **"mind"** is part of a person's brain to remember things, while the literal meaning of **"up"** is in or into a higher position or level. According to the Dictionary of American Idioms, there is an idiom **"make up"**

one's mind" which is equivalent to the idiom **"made my mind up"** because some words are the same. The meaning of this idiom is to choose what to do; decide.

3. Irreversible Binomial Idiom

According to Makkai (1994), an Irreversible Binomial Idiom is an idiom that is made up of two words joined by a conjunction. In this research, the researcher found 1 Irreversible Binomial Idiom. The examples are as follows:

a. Example 1

Idiomatic expression : More and more
Title of song : Halloween
Lyrics : **"more and more, I'll catalogue my doubts"**
Context : He will organize his thoughts even better

In the 3rd line of the Halloween song lyrics, "more and more, I'll catalogue my doubts", there is an idiom **"more and more"**. This idiom is categorized as an Irreversible Binomial Idiom type, which contains the conjunction **"and"** that forms a format of Irreversible Binomial Idiom in which the word A and the word B are regarded as the same word. The idiom **"more and more"** takes the literal meaning of **"more"**, which means in addition or something additional; a greater quantity, number, or amount. The meaning of the idiom **"more and more"**, based on The Free Online Dictionary, is increasingly, or an increasing number of something.

4. Phrasal Compound Idiom

According to Makkai (1994), a Phrasal Compound Idiom is commonly an idiom whose words are united into one and form a single thought. In this research, the researcher found 8 Phrasal Compound Idioms. The examples are as follows:

a. Example 1

Idiomatic expression : Bleeding sun
Title of song : No Plans
Lyrics : "sweat it out, cold, 'till you're **bleeding sun**"
Context : He asks his lover to wait for an unpleasant situation to end until she loses all her love for him.

In the 4th line of the No Plans song lyrics, "sweat it out, cold, 'till you're bleeding sun", there is an idiom **"bleeding sun"**. This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Compound Idiom type, which is formed from Noun + Noun. The meaning of the idiom **"bleeding sun"** has nothing to do with the literal meaning of **"bleeding"** and **"sun"**. The phrase **"bleeding sun"** seems to make no sense if taken literally. According to Baker (2011), interpreting an idiom can be done by looking for an idiom of similar meaning and form in idiom dictionaries. Therefore, to interpret it, one must adapt to other similar idioms. The meaning of this idiom can be adapted for the word **"bleeding"** to be interpreted as the loss of one's resources. On the other hand, in the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Online Dictionary, there is an idiom **"think the sun shines out (of) somebody's arse/backside"**, which means to love and admire someone so much that you do not think they have any bad qualities. This idiom emphasizes the word **"sun"** in interpreting the meaning, which leads to the conclusion that the meaning of the sun is love or admiration. Therefore, the meaning of the idiom **"bleeding sun"** is lost a lot of love or admiration.

b. Example 2

Idiomatic expression : Feeling low

Title of song : Opaline

Lyrics : "I know, I could've said I was **feeling low**"

Context : He knows that he can say that he is tired or sad.

In the 13th line of the Opaline song lyrics, "I know, I could've said I was feeling low", there is an idiom "**feeling low**". This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Compound Idiom type, which is formed from Noun + Adjective. The idiom "**feeling low**" contains the literal meaning of "**feeling**", which means emotion, and the literal meaning of "**low**", which means weak or depressed. The meaning of the idiom "**feeling low**" can be adapted from the idiom "**feeling down**" because of the synonyms for "**low**" and "**down**", taken from the Dictionary of American Idioms, which means feeling tired, miserable, exhausted, sad, or depressed.

c. Example 3

Idiomatic expression : Stay awake

Title of song : Halloween

Lyrics : "by the age of 28, I can barely **stay awake**"

Context : As he gets older, he may not always be aware of something.

In the 6th line of the Halloween song lyrics, "by the age of 28, I can barely stay awake", there is an idiom "**stay awake**". This idiom is categorized as a Phrasal Compound Idiom type, which is formed from Verb + Adjective. The meaning of this idiom has nothing to do with the literal meaning of "**awake**", which means not asleep. Therefore, the meaning of the idiom "**stay awake**" can be equated with the idiom "**stay up**" because the synonym of the word "**awake**" is "**wake up**". This idiom, taken from The Free Online Dictionary, has the meaning: 1) to remain awake. 2) to remain on display. 3) to remain well informed. The interpretation of this idiom can still confuse, despite the first meaning, which is to remain awake.

5. Discussion

After obtaining and analyzing the data from the song lyrics, the next part is the discussion of the whole dataset to answer the problem proposed in the previous chapter. The problem statement is a question of what the types of idioms in the song lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor are. Dealing with the answer, the types of idiomatic expressions in this album are four types of idioms by the theory of Makkai (1994). They are Phrasal Verb Idiom, Tournure Idiom, Irreversible Binomial Idiom, and Phrasal Compound Idiom.

The first type is Phrasal Verb Idiom. According to Makkai (1994), an idiom can be classified as a Phrasal Verb Idiom if it includes a verb and a particle (adverb and/or preposition). Phrasal verbs are usually used in everyday English usage as the new way verbs enter the English language and become recognized as acceptable standard usage. However, there is a difference between Phrasal Verb Idioms and phrasal verbs. The difference is in the use of the literal meaning of the word. The only way to differentiate it is memorizing the phrasal verb along with its meaning and use, or look it up in an idiom dictionary, as the researchers did in this study.

The Tournure Idiom is the second type. This type is the dominant idiom type found in the research. According to Makkai (1994), a Tournure Idiom type is the largest lexemic idiom type, it has a bigger size level than the other idioms that have only two words and word-level idioms. This idiom has at least three words. In song lyrics, Tournure Idiom can even be written as only one line. Some signs can clearly distinguish the Tournure Idiom from other types of idioms from Makkai's theory. In addition to the number of words that have at least three words, most Tournure Idioms have a format, such as where there is the compulsory "it" and the compulsory definite and indefinite articles. It can be seen that Novo Amor uses a lot of this idiom type because he wants to express his lyrics with longer idioms so that the lyrics have a deeper impression.

The third type is the Irreversible Binomial Idiom. According to Makkai (1994), an Irreversible Binomial Idiom is an idiom that is made up of two words joined by a conjunction. In this form, the word order is stable and permanent. Irreversible Binomials signify pairs of words that are teamed up based on some kind of connection between them. Only by being used in pairs and one specific order can they convey the entirety of the expression without sounding a little off to trained ears. What order they will be used in and with what conjunctions will depend on how the native speakers have been using them over the years. However, this idiom type is the least found, and the only one that is the "more and more" expression. The reason Novo Amor does not use more conjunction idioms could be because he is less interested in the figurative language of comparison or equality. It can be seen that the lyrics of the song that he wrote put more emphasis on showing the idiom directly so that listeners don't have to double think about comparisons or similarities of things.

The last type that the researcher found is Phrasal Compound Idiom. According to Makkai (1994), a Phrasal Compound Idiom is commonly an idiom whose words are united into one and form a single thought. This is a common form of idiom. Some words are combined into one, but their meaning is not based on their constituent elements. This class contains primary nominals made up of variations of word combinations. It can function as a verb, adjective, or noun. This idiom type is often equated with Phrasal Verb Idiom because phrasal verbs are part of a phrasal compound. However, Makkai's theory states that any combination of two words other than verb + adverb, then it is a Phrasal Compound Idiom. This may be done to ease the categorization.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion in the previous chapter, there is a conclusion in this study as a result of answering the research question. There were 63 idiomatic expressions found in the song lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor. The idioms were categorized into Makkai's idiom classification theory which were 10 Phrasal Verb Idioms, 44 Tournure Idioms, 1 Irreversible Binomial Idiom, and 8 Phrasal Compound Idioms. Based on the data found, it showed the dominant idiom type in the album "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" was the Tournure Idiom because there are more three words found in the data. Meanwhile, the least type was the Irreversible Binomial Idiom, which only consisted of a conjunction between two words. The researcher did not find the type of Incorporating Verb Idiom.

Besides that, to understand the idioms better, the researcher also tried to find the meanings of the idioms. The meaning of the idiomatic expressions found in this research has been interpreted using an idiom dictionary by using an idiom of similar meaning and form. Some idiom dictionaries such as the Dictionary of American Idioms, the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms, The Free Online Dictionary, the Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary, and the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Online Dictionary have been used by the researcher to verify the idiomatic expressions and find the meaning of the idioms found in the song lyrics of the "Cannot Be, Whatsoever" album by Novo Amor.

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